

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTIC BANDS OF IR SPECTRA OF TBSC AND ITS COMPLEXES

TBSC	Mn(II)	Fe(II)	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Zn(II)	Assignment
...	3450	3360	3480	3460	3470	3420	ν O-H
8140	8120	8107	8120	8120	8110	8120	ν N-H
3020	3000	2980	3020	3020	3020	2997	ν C-H
1670	...	...	...	...	...	...	ν C=O
...	1680	1695	1685	1680	1685	1680	δ H ₂ O
1645	1630	1630	1635	1630	1630	1635	ν C=N
...	1570	1550	1550	1560	1550	1560	ν C=N-N=C
1510	1520	1510	1510	1520	1510	1515	ν C-N
...	1280	1290	1290	1280	1285	1285	δ N-H
...	520	520	515	515	510	520	ν C-O
...	455	460	455	465	460	450	ν M-O
							ν M-N

site, respectively, indicating coordination of the ligand in enolic form to the metals. A negative shift in the stretching frequency of C=N (azomethine) group suggests the coordination of azomethine nitrogens. The coordination of azomethine nitrogen is also supported by a positive shift in the stretching vibrations of N-N group^r in the spectra of the complexes. The coordination through oxygen and nitrogen is further confirmed by the occurrence of new bands at ca 520-510 and 460-450 in the spectra of the complexes, which may be assigned to M-O and M-N stretching frequencies, respectively⁸. The strong bands observed in the complexes in the region 3500-3300 and ca 1690 may be assigned to ν OH(H₂O) and δ H₂O respectively, and indicate the presence of lattice and/or crystallization and/or coordination water in the complexes⁹.

(III)

Thus, the TBSC acts as tetradentate chelating agent, coordinating through the enolic oxygens and azomethine nitrogens, and polymeric complexes are formed (structure III) as the steric factors prevent the coordination of all the donor groups to the same metal ion.

TBSC is yellow in colour and therefore severely restricts the utility and accuracy of the electronic spectral studies, since intraligand bands interfere with the d-d bands of transition metal ions in the electronic spectra of the complexes.

The drs of TBSC shows strong band with its λ_{max} at 380 nm (26,300 cm⁻¹) with a minor peak on the lower wavelength side at 270 nm (37,000 cm⁻¹). On the higher side absorption decreases more rapidly but it does not disappear up to 840 nm. The bands in the ligand may be assigned to the intraligand transitions, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$.

The observed magnetic moment of Mn(II)-complex is 5.89 B.M. which is in accordance with the value expected for spin only value for five

unpaired electrons in an octahedral Mn(II)-complex involving sp^{3d} hybridization. The reflectance spectrum shows weak bands at 16,130, 21,740, 27,780, 29,410 and 31,000 cm⁻¹. The three higher bands have been assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (G), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (G) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$ (G) and the two lower bands to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (D) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$ (D) respectively, in an octahedral field of Mn(II) ion^{10,11}.

The observed magnetic moment of Co(II)-complex is 4.87 B.M. In drs of Co(II)-complex, two bands appear at 10,000 and 22,900 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}$ (F) $\rightarrow$ ${}^4T_{2g}$ (F) (ν_1) and ${}^4T_{1g}$ (F) $\rightarrow$ ${}^4T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_2). However, the ${}^4T_{1g}$ (F) $\rightarrow$ ${}^4A_{2g}$ (F) (ν_3) transition is not observed, since it is a two electron process and has a much lower oscillator strength than the other two transitions, and is therefore much weaker. The values of 10 Dq and ν_3 have been calculated to be 11,350 and 21,350 cm⁻¹, respectively. The ν_3/ν_1 ratio, which is found to be 2.13, lies within the limit (2.1-2.2) reported for octahedral Co(II)-complexes¹².

The electronic spectrum of Ni(II)-complex shows three d-d transition bands at 10,526, 15,652 and 26,319 cm⁻¹ which correspond to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (F) (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3), respectively. The ν_3/ν_1 ratio is 1.50. The magnetic moment value (2.94 B.M.) together with drs data shows the octahedral geometry of Ni(II)-complex.

Cu(II)-complex has a magnetic moment value of 1.79 B.M. The electronic configuration 3d⁹ gives rise to 2D free ion term which splits in a regular octahedral environment into a lower doublet 2E_g and an upper triplet ${}^2T_{2g}$ levels. In electronic spectrum, only one band due to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition is expected but true octahedral structures are uncommon. Here, three bands appear as shoulders at 10,000, 11,110 and 15,150 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions, respectively in a distorted octahedral geometry of Cu(II) ion¹⁴.

The thermal stability data of the complexes show that the initial weight loss is probably due to the loss of water molecules present in the complexes. The weight loss at the temperatures between 180-220° corresponds closely to water content of the chelates. On further heating, the organic component of the complexes decomposes leading to the formation of metal oxides. The order of thermal stability is Zn > Ni > Co > Mn > Cu.

The geometry of the ligand, composition, insolubility and thermal stability of complexes indicate that they are polymeric in nature¹⁻⁴.

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